

International Conference on Motherhood Melodies: A Global Harmony of Literary Resonance

The International Conference on Motherhood Melodies: A Global Harmony of Literary Resonance, organized by the Postgraduate Department of English in association with IQAC at Christ Nagar College, served as a vibrant platform for scholars and enthusiasts to explore the multifaceted themes surrounding motherhood in literature. This conference brought together diverse voices from around the globe, fostering rich discussions on the cultural, emotional, and artistic representations of motherhood. Participants engaged in thought-provoking panels, workshops, and keynote speeches that delved into the intersections of literary tradition and contemporary narratives. The proceedings highlight not only the personal and societal implications of motherhood but also celebrate its profound influence on literary expression, ensuring that the dialogue continues to resonate far beyond the event itself.

Attendees also had the opportunity to share their own research and creative works, contributing to an atmosphere of collaboration and innovation. By weaving together perspectives from various disciplines and cultures, the conference illuminated the enduring power of motherhood as a theme that transcends boundaries, inviting new interpretations and fostering a deeper understanding of its significance in our lives and literature.

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